

D5.4 Stakeholder Engagement Roadmap

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Short Description

This report outlines the process of identifying stakeholders, defining key touchpoints for interaction, and designing engagement strategies. It details the initiatives and actions taken to involve stakeholders effectively, ensuring meaningful participation and collaboration throughout the first half of the project.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
EDIH	European Digital Innovation Hub
HE	Higher Education
I5.0	Industry 5.0
I5.C	Industry 5.0 Community of Interest
LE	Large Enterprise
LP	Lead Partner (Flanders Make)
NSB	NSBproject
PP	Project Partner
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
TPF	Technology partners
UNIMORE	Università degli Studi di Modena e Reggio Emilia

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

European industry is a key driver in the currently undergoing twin green and digital transition. The success of the digital transition, in particular, will strongly depend on an increased autonomy in key strategic value chains with security of supply in raw materials as well on a human-centred and ethical development of digital and industrial technologies, through a two-way engagement in the development of technologies, empowering end-users and workers, and supporting social innovation.

The global objective of the PROSPECTS 5.0 project is to facilitate the successful transition to Industry 5.0 by providing practical guidance, tools, and solutions to policy makers and industry stakeholders, enhancing skills, awareness, and acceptance among workers and end-users.

Fostering cooperation among key stakeholders, the project examines how human centricity, sustainability, and resiliency are adopted by businesses of all sizes across industries to support their Industry 5.0 transition. It fosters collaboration among key stakeholders and develops measurement tools to assess impact, offering policy recommendations.

Building on this foundation, a dedicated project task (led by NSBproject) has been developed aiming at strengthening stakeholder engagement and nurturing the Industry 5.0 Community of Interest (I5.C) as a strategic pillar of the project. It pursues three main objectives:

1. To strengthen stakeholder engagement by identifying relevant actors and building meaningful connections across the Industry 5.0 ecosystem, through the main activities of the project.
2. To nurture the I5.C through a co-creative approach that actively involves project partners, community members, and related initiatives aligned with PROSPECTS 5.0.
3. To maximize the impact and added value of key project outputs - such as Wiki5.0 and the Assessment Framework- by ensuring these tools are shaped by, and useful to, organisations addressing real Industry 5.0 challenges.

By aligning engagement activities with these objectives, the task ensures a collaborative and needs-driven contribution to the project's broader goals.

This report outlines the process of identifying stakeholders, defining key touchpoints for interaction, and designing engagement strategies. It details the initiatives and actions taken to involve stakeholders effectively, ensuring meaningful participation and collaboration throughout the first half of the project.

2. INTRODUCTION

This document, aimed at mapping the stakeholders' engagement carried out so far by NSB in cooperation with partners, outlines the following:

- a) The I5.C engagement process, with a focus on:
 - The analysis and identification of the Community of Interest members
 - The invitation process to become member of the Community of Interest
 - The categorization of members
 - The engagement activities implemented
 - Approaches and tools adopted as well as the activities carried out to create and nurture the I5.0 Community of Interest

- b) The SISTER projects engagement process, with a focus on:
 - The selection of projects with linkages with PROSPECTS 5.0
 - The invitation to the stakeholder event
 - The analysis of their aims and touch points with PROSPECTS 5.0
 - The engagement activities implemented
 - The approaches and tools adopted
 - I5.0 Community of Interest members

- c) The consortium partners engagement process, with a focus on:
 - The involvement in the I5.C creation and nurturing
 - The engagement in the Wiki 5.0 creation and nurturing
 - The involvement in the Assessment framework design and validation process
 - The co-creation of the exploitation process

3. 15.0 COMMUNITY OF INTEREST MEMBERS

3.1. Identification of Type of Stakeholders

In order to involve the most suitable organisations/people in the 15.0 Community of Interest and in the project as a whole, an initial identification of the most relevant profiles was carried out.

In cooperation with the project coordinator and the partners, the following types of actors were identified as the most fitting within the scope of this project:

- EU Association
- DIH (Digital Innovation Hub)
- EDIH (European Digital Innovation Hub)
- Lab or other facility
- R&D organization
- University & HE (Higher Education)
- SME (Small and Medium Enterprise)
- LE (Large Enterprise)
- Industry Association, Cluster & similar
- Policy stakeholder
- Advisory Board member
- Other

Then partnership decided to involve:

- project use cases (SMEs or LEs) to provide and share 5.0 concrete practices within the Community of Interest as well as to support use cases with shared knowledge about the sector
- project Associated partners to have on board a complementary expertise within the Community of interest, to share their knowledge and give them the opportunity to be part of an innovative framework
- Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs) connected to some project partners have been involved to bring complementary expertise, leverage established collaborations, and share specialised knowledge with the Community of Interest.
- EDIH relevant for the project for their expertise, for their capability at local or regional level to share practices, tools and sources about 5.0 with SMEs and Large companies (their business ecosystem)
- EU associations to share knowledge, tools and cross-fertilize practices.

With regard to EDIH and DIH, a selection from the EDIH catalogue (from a list of 138) was made by NSB in cooperation with the Lead Partner (Flanders Make) (LP) (through a dedicated online bilateral meeting), using the following filters:

- Funded EDIHs
- Technologies: all but chemical engineering, gamification, industrial biotechnology, location-based applications, new technologies for audio-visual sector; organic and large area electronics

Therefore, we selected the Hubs that:

- mentioned/have partners who represent companies or who are relevant companies (not only HEI or Research)
- mentioned interest in the Industry 5.0/resilience/human centricity, sustainability in their presentation/services (few of them)

Invitations and reminders to the EDIHs have been sent starting from July 2024 on, by e-mail and/or dedicated meeting calls.

Project partners with EDIHs in their own ecosystem were committed to their engagement in the I5.0 Community of interest.

3.2. Categorization and Customization

It was crucial to identify needs and expectations of the I5.C members, this is the reason why NSB designed and activated, with the support of INTRACT¹, the online registration form (as a Letter of intent, as agreed with LP) aiming at:

- "formalizing" the membership in the Community of interest
- select the main fields of interest of the members to match the project offer

Therefore, the stakeholders, in the online registration process, have been (and are) invited to select among the following options from a drop-down menu:

- 5.0 scientific knowledge and updates,
- 5.0 assessment level,
- Wiki 5.0 repository,
- 5.0 industry practices for inspiration,
- 5.0 use cases,
- 5.0 drivers and benefits,
- Other, please specify

¹ <https://prospects5-0.eu/#getinvolved>

Want to become a part of the transition towards Industry 5.0?

Industry 5.0 Community of Interest

Becoming a member of the I5.0 Community of Interest, which consists of EU actors and organisations with various backgrounds (companies with their case studies, DIH and EDIH, project advisory board, EU working groups dealing with Industry 5.0 concepts, and industry associations), opens the door to:

- share know-how on current Industry 5.0 practices and gaps
- access ongoing studies on Industry 5.0 (drivers, benefits, etc.)
- contribute to the definition of an Industry 5.0 assessment
- access and contribute to the WIKI 5.0 repository,
- be inspired by 5.0 practices in different industrial sectors.

As a member of the I5.0 community, you will be involved from time to time in (online) workshops and feedback surveys according to your specific profile, thus acting an active role in the definition of a common framework for Industry 5.0.

Organisation Name *

Country *

Project Partner *

Type *

First Name *

Last Name *

Email *

Main interest in the community *

By clicking here, I accept the [privacy policy](#). *

I agree to become a member of the Industry 5.0 Community of Interest and subscribe to the newsletter! *

* This field required

Submit Form

Figure 1 Community of Interest I5.0 subscription form screenshot

The selection of areas of interest allows to have a segmentation of people to whom to propose activities and updates more targeted to their needs.

A dedicated database – available in the PROSPECTS 5.0 share point – was created to collect all the relevant information, aimed at mapping all actors invited to join/who joined the I5.0 Community of interest.

The I5.C database is collecting the following information:

- Organisation name
- Project Partner (Y/N)
- Country
- Type (from the list mentioned above)
- Name
- Email
- Main interest in the Community of Interest (selection made among the following options: 5.0 Knowledge and updates; 5.0 drivers and benefits; 5.0 industry practices for inspiration; 5.0 use cases; 5.0 Assessment level; wiki 5.0 repository; Other)

To date, the Community of Interest (now counting over 50 members²) consists primarily of EDIHs, SMEs, and higher education institutions, with solid representation from large enterprises and R&D organisations, as illustrated in the Figure 2.

Figure 2 Composition of the I5.0 Community of interest

As shown in the Figure 3, the Community of interest’s primary interests lie in exploring Industry 5.0 practices for inspiration and gaining insights from the PROSPECTS 5.0 use cases:

Figure 3 Main fields of interest of the I5.0 Community of interest

The following main phases of the project are/were found to be essential for the involvement of the I5.C, namely:

² See Annex 1 for details

- co-creation and validation of the Industry 5.0 Assessment Framework
- workshops and or data collection for the self-assessment tool
- team building events
- developing policy recommendations
- evaluation of the PROSPECTS 5.0 platform

3.3. Engagement

The initial members, as well as other potential members of the I5.0 Community of interest, were invited to join the first stakeholder engagement event organised in May 2024 in Brussels by the Project Leader (Task 1.1).

In October 2024, ahead of the General meeting in Brussels, a coordinated engagement plan was led by NSB and co-designed with several key project partners - including Flanders Make, Tecnalia, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Aethon, Technological Centre Latvia, Technology Partners, and Intract – to structure meaningful interactions with the I5.C.

These engagement actions were aligned with specific project outcomes, and included the following contributions:

- AETHON shaped its plan to collect feedback on the PROSPECTS 5.0 platform;
- Intract shared its plan to gather contributions and suggestions for the development of Wiki5.0;
- Tecnalia shaped its plan about the knowledge-sharing initiatives through thematic workshops;
- Technology Partners shared its commitment in ensuring consistent updates via communication and dissemination activities;
- Latvian Technological Centre anticipated that conduct online interviews to support the development of policy recommendations;
- NSB shared its commitment in the involvement of relevant actors, leveraging the stakeholder interest mapping and customization analysis.

Additionally, in October 2024, members of the Advisory Board were invited to join the Community of Interest and were actively involved in providing feedback on the Assessment Framework with a dedicated meeting managed by the LP and UNIIMORE.

The 14 use cases participating in the project also contributed to the feedback process of the Framework, which is planned to be validated in real-world conditions throughout 2025.

In December 2024, an online meeting was organised by NSB with INTRACT and Technology Partners to outline the next steps for several tasks within the PROSPECTS 5.0 project.

Below is a summary of the key decisions and actions that followed.

- Task 2.3 – Team Building and Mutual Learning (Led by TECNALIA):
The first workshop was designed to reflect on progress made so far; therefore, Community of Interest members were not directly involved in evaluating the added value of PROSPECTS 5.0 at this stage.

However, following discussions with TECNALIA and selected partners, it was agreed to involve external stakeholders as guest speakers to promote mutual learning. As a result, EIT Manufacturing and EDIH DIHNAMO – both members of the I5.C – were invited as key contributors. Two preparatory meetings were held on January 23 and February 3 to finalise their participation.

The resulting workshop, titled “Industry 5.0 in Action: Business Experiences and Expert Insights,” took place online on March 19, engaging both project partners and I5.0 Community of Interest members (representing 25% of attendees).

Here is the official invitation text:

*SUBJECT: Have your say at our Exclusive Industry 5.0 event
on March 19!*

Dear Mrs/Mr,

*As member of the **PROSPECTS 5.0 Community of interest of Interest we** are excited to invite you to our **first online restricted workshop!***

 March 19, 2025 at 10am – INDUSTRY 5.0 IN ACTION: BUSINESS EXPERIENCES & EXPERT INSIGHTS

*This exclusive online event will showcase real-world applications and challenges of **Industry 5.0**, featuring expert insights and interactive discussions on how businesses across Europe are embracing (or wary of) this transformation.*

We'd love for you to join us—check out the details below and reserve your spot!

Here is the agenda of the event:

PROSPECTS 5.0

**INDUSTRY 5.0 IN ACTION:
Business Experiences
& Expert Insights**

Online Workshop | **19 March 2025-10:00-12:00**

The times in the calendar are set in Central European Time (CET), ie in the (GMT+2) time zone.

Organized by PROSPECTS 5.0, this exclusive event showcases how Industry 5.0 principles are transforming businesses across Europe shaping the future.

This workshop will bring previous experiences from the industry partners of PROSPECTS 5.0 and relevant stakeholders. It will provide a space for team building, mutual learning from best practices and learned lessons.

Discover how **5 innovative companies** are applying Industry 5.0 principles:

- **GTW Bearings (Czechia)** – *Bearing manufacturing*
- **TRYGONS (Greece)** – *Composite parts for marine & automotive*
- **CAMELEO (Poland)** – *Custom decorative coatings*
- **S-Gard (Germany)** – *Safety gear manufacturing*
- **ZEUKO (Spain)** – *Cranes, lifting systems and heavy equipment*

Special Guests: EIT Manufacturing & DIHNAMO EDIH

Get ready for **Expert Insights & Interactive Discussion** to exchange ideas & explore Industry 5.0 solutions!

Registration & Agenda:

prospects5-0.eu/owi5insights

Figure 4 Agenda of the first workshop on Mutual learning

Following the first workshop, which gathered 36 participants, including 21 members of the I5.C, a survey was launched to gather input on the key challenges and topics participants wished to explore further in the future.

The survey was jointly developed by NSB, TECNALIA, and Technology Partners, and distributed to the I5.C members by INTRACT. Results indicated a strong level of satisfaction regarding relevance, alignment with expectations, and overall usefulness (average score: 8 across all categories). The feedback also highlighted a clear demand for more practical insights, especially regarding the challenges and solutions encountered during the transition to Industry 5.0. These findings were shared with TECNALIA to inspire the design of a more targeted and meaningful second workshop, that was addressed to project partners during the project meeting that was held in Modena (May 2025). This second session focused on showcasing the engagement and the interim impact of the PROSPECTS 5.0 project on the Industry 5.0 transformation journey within project use cases.

- **Task 3.3 – Development of the PROSPECTS 5.0 Platform (Led by AETHON)**
The platform is set to be launched by December 2025, with an initial focus on engaging LEs and SMEs from the I5.0 Community of interest. These stakeholders will be invited to provide structured feedback on the platform's usability, content, and relevance. To support this process, NSB will organise a

preparatory meeting in October 2025, followed by dedicated support from INTRACT and NSB to help AETHON identify and involve the most suitable Community of Interest members.

- Task 4.2 – Policy Recommendations (Led by LTC)

Scheduled for December 2025, this task will include online interviews with selected stakeholders to inform the project’s policy recommendations. To prepare for this activity, NSB will organise a coordination meeting in October 2025, after which INTRACT and NSB will assist LTC in selecting and engaging the most relevant I5.0 Community of Interest members to contribute meaningfully to the design of the policy recommendations.

- Task 5.1 – Dissemination and Communication Activities (Led by TPF)

The second project newsletter was set for release in the first quarter of 2025. To enhance engagement and tailor future editions to the interests of the Community of interest, TPF will prepare a feedback survey using the EU Survey platform. The survey will be finalised in collaboration with Flanders Make, INTRACT, and NSB by May 2025, and will gather input on both content relevance and format.

- Task 5.2 – PROSPECTS 5.0 Wiki (Led by INTRACT)

During the first quarter of 2025, Community of Interest members will be invited to explore and contribute to Wiki5.0, by sharing their knowledge, experiences, tools, and references in relevant sections.

To support platform improvement, INTRACT, together with TPF, will develop a dedicated feedback survey in April 2025 (coordinated with the survey from Task 5.1) aimed at capturing insights to enhance the platform’s usefulness and usability.

A more detailed plan is illustrated in the figure below. This planning tool has been shared with all partners and completed by the task leaders responsible for key engagement activities identified throughout the project, highlighting tasks, roles, periods and type of actors to be engaged.

PROSPECTS 5.0 (1 Jan. 24 - 31 Dec. 26) - I5.0 Community engagement activities

Figure 5 Touch points for the I5.0 Community of Interest engagement

The online meeting held on April 3rd with Technology Partners, NSB and ARTES5.0 (a Competence Centre with its own EDIH) provided valuable inspiration for future engagement opportunities.

Key ideas discussed during the meeting included:

- Interviewing selected Community of Interest members (from diverse categories such as EDIHs, research centres, universities, etc.) to gather their perspectives on Industry 5.0. These insights could be shared through social media, newsletters, or the project website.
- Involving ARTES5.0 as a contributor to Wiki5.0, in addition to the wider call for contributions already planned with Kubra.
- Engaging ARTES5.0 in upcoming events or joint initiatives where they can present their I5.0 best practices and inspire a broader audience.

The general meeting held in person in May 2025 in Modena served as a key moment to deepen and refine the project's engagement strategy.

During the dedicated sessions on WP5, particular attention was given to aligning tasks and goals with partners to ensure a coordinated and impactful approach.

This collaborative effort reinforced a structured pathway for stakeholder involvement, ensuring that upcoming activities are tailored also to the diverse roles and profiles within the I5.C and ultimately fostering more meaningful participation and collaboration.

4. SISTER PROJECTS

4.1. The Projects

As envisaged by the PROSPECTS 5.0 project, a selection of potential ‘SISTER’ projects was made by the project coordinator, i.e. other EU projects focused on I5.0 with which to create cooperation and complementary actions.

The project leaders of the selected projects were invited to take part in the event “Towards the Industry 5.0 – a need for change: Theory vs. Practice” where project partners and other stakeholders were involved.

During the event, that was organised by Flanders Make and took place in Brussels in May 2024, we got in touch and agreed to start collaborating with the following projects, because of their linkages and potential synergies with PROSPECTS 5.0, namely:

- AIREGIO5.0
Regions and (E)DIHs alliance for AI-at-the-Edge adoption by European Industry 5.0 Manufacturing SMEs
- BRIDGES5.0
Towards a Human-Centred, Sustainable and Resilient Economy | Workforce Skills for Industry 5.0
- SEISMEC
Piloting the Shift to Human-Centric Industry | A journey towards a skills-driven and creativity-infused industrial landscape

4.2. Engagement

A series of collaborative activities have been planned and executed to strengthen synergies among SISTER projects.

On July 2024, an online meeting was organized with AIDREGIO 5.0, SEISMEC, and BRIDGES5.0 to align objectives and discuss engagement strategies.

To facilitate collaboration, a shared timeline was developed to initiate engagement activities, along with an infographic outlining the cooperation process (Figure 6)

These materials have been stored in a dedicated collaboration folder (created in the PROSPECTS 5.0 SharePoint) accessible to all SISTER projects.

Figure 6 SISTER projects: Cross - fertilization pathway

Additionally, an invitation was extended to all SISTER projects to become members of the I5.0 Community of interest, fostering broader participation.

Further steps in the collaboration included a meeting on October 10, 2024, with Steven Dhondt, coordinator of BRIDGES5.0, to define key tasks and explore opportunities for cross-fertilization. This was followed by a demonstration of the BRIDGES platform on October 14, 2024, providing valuable insights into its functionalities.

On October 28, 2024, a meeting with the SEISMEC communication team was held to coordinate outreach efforts, and on November 6, 2024, further discussions took place with the stakeholder engagement lead for BRIDGES5.0 to align approaches for involvement.

In addition, a workshop on the Assessment Framework was conducted on November 19, 2024, in collaboration with SISTER projects, promoting knowledge exchange and shared learning.

To further streamline joint efforts, a coordination meeting was held on January 30, 2025, with COMM&DISS lead partners from SEISMEC, BRIDGES 5.0 and AIDREGIO 5.0 to schedule upcoming activities. A periodic update meeting with COMM&DISS teams of the SISTER projects has been agreed to be held online.

An update meeting was held on March 27, 2025, with SISTER projects and synergies were agreed for Wiki 5.0 (BRIDGES 5.0 provided an input in terms of Training opportunities for I5.0 skills and the PROSPECTS 5.0 team will provide information in the BRIDGES open lab about the use cases once the Assessment Framework will be advanced).

A common framework (see Figure below) was also designed to enable each project team to visualize time plans and identify potential synergies with the activities (and task leader) planned by the PROSPECTS 5.0 project and by BRIDGES5.0, SEISMEC and AIREDGIO5.0.

PROSPECTS 5.0 (1 Jan. 24 - 31 Dec. 26) & SISTER projects

ACTIVITY	START	DURATION	PROSPECTS Involved	BRIDGES 5.0	BRIDGES Actions Involved	SISIMAC	SISIMAC SISTER Involved	AMBICO 5.0	AMBICO Involved	2024												2025												2026											
										1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
PROSPECTS 5.0 Duration	1	36	FM & AI	/	/	/	/	/	/																																				
TS.1 JOINT DISS	1	36	TFP	X	Workplace Innov. Europe	X	Autotolo	X	AFL																																				
TS.3 COMMUNITY OF INTEREST	1	36	NSB	X	KU Leuven	X	TNO	X	Polimi																																				
TS.2 WORKY 5.0	4	33	INTRACT	X	Workplace Innov. Europe	X	TNO	X	Polimi																																				
TS.3 ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORK VALID.	6	7	UNWACRE	X	Workplace Innov. Europe	X	EUR	X	Polimi																																				
TS.2 DEVELOP. OF IS.0 ASSESSMENT REPORTS	20	11	AETHON	X	Workplace Innov. Europe	X	EUR/TNO	X	Polimi																																				
TS.5.5.0 PLATFORM	24	36	AETHON	X	Workplace Innov. Europe	X	TNO	X	Polimi																																				
TS.2 POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS	24	13	LTC	X	KU Leuven	X	TNO	X	Polimi																																				
JOINT PARTICIPATION IN EVENTS	9	36	FM & TFP	X	TNO	X	Autotolo	X	Polimi																																				
MODELS & TOOLS SHARING	9	36	FM& ALL	X	TNO	X	EUR/TNO	X	Polimi																																				

Figure 7 Timeline for SISTER projects' synergies

Lastly, cooperation with BRIDGES5.0 has led to an initiative involving Community of Interest members and partners in preparing a paper for the conference "Advancing Industry 5.0: Building Skills, Enhancing Employee Voice, and Driving Workplace Innovation", that will be held in June 2025 in Leuven. A call for participation was sent to partners and shared with the broader Community of Interest to encourage engagement in this initiative.

Here is the engaging text:

Exciting Opportunity for Our Community of interest!

Allison Dunne, leader of the Community of Interest for BRIDGES5.0 (one of our SISTER projects), has reached out with the official announcement of the Advancing Industry 5.0 Conference!

◆ *They are calling on PROSPECTS 5.0 partners and our IS.0 Community of Interest (researchers, practitioners and thought leaders) to contribute!*

Are you ready to share your insights? Look at the call for paper (attached to this message) and submit an abstract on one of these key topics:

- ◆ *Track 1: Employee Participation and the Transition to Industry 5.0*
- ◆ *Track 2: Developing Skills and Creating Learning Organisations for Industry 5.0*
- ◆ *Track 3: Strengthening Employee Voice in the Workplace*

 Key Dates to Remember:

March 21, 2025 – Abstract submission deadline

April 30, 2025 – Acceptance decisions

May 5, 2025 – Deadline for presenting attendees

May 23, 2025 – Conference registration deadline

June 16-17, 2025 – Conference in Leuven, Belgium

Interested?

Let us know – we'd love to see strong contributions from our network!

The PROSPECTS 5.0 partner Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia applied for this call with its paper and was selected.

The PROSPECTS 5.0 project will be represented there by the project coordinator (Flanders Make).

With regard to joint newsletters here are the links of the joint communication (project website/LinkedIn/newsletter) designed with sister projects so far:

a) PROSPECTS 5.0

- On the project website: [here](#)
- On the newsletters:
 - [Newsletter 1](#)
 - [Newsletter 2](#)
- On LinkedIn:
 - [Tech-savvy Call](#)
 - [Advancing Industry 5.0 Conference](#)
 - [SEISMEC Shift: CAPS Framework](#)
 - [The Second Open Call of #AIREDGIO50](#)
 - [Sister Projects](#)

b) AIREDGIO 5.0

- On LinkedIn:
 - [Introducing the Industry 5.0 Wiki](#)
 - [Industry 5.0 \(1.5\) stakeholder event in Brussels](#)

c) SEISMEC

- On LinkedIn:
 - [SEISMEC Newswave #2](#)
 - [Advancing Industry 5.0 Conference](#)
 - [Fresh newsletter from PROSPECTS 5.0 Horizon Europe Project!](#)
 - [Monday's session with our sister project](#)
 - [Industry 5.0 Wiki is live](#)
 - [The PROSPECTS 5.0 Horizon Europe Project stakeholder event in Brussels](#)
 - [From major conferences to impactful workshops](#)

d) BRIDGES 5.0

- On project website:
 - [A Collaborative Partnership](#)

In addition, the four projects — PROSPECTS 5.0, AIREDGIO 5.0, BRIDGES 5.0, and SEISMEC — are planning to co-organize a joint event in the first quarter of 2026 addressed to the relevant enterprise actors interested in 5.0 transition.

The goal is to enhance the visibility and value of their respective outcomes and tools by presenting them as part of a cohesive support ecosystem.

A proposed central theme for the event is: "Industry 5.0 and the Geopolitical Context: Impacts and Opportunities for Businesses" – a topic that will be further developed through joint brainstorming meetings.

5. PROJECT PARTNERS

The role of project partners was pivotal in the identification of the actors (stakeholders) to be involved in the I5.0 Community of interest, they were involved in the categorization process as well as in the (ongoing) nurturing of the I5.0 Community of interest, exploiting the added value of their own ecosystem and network.

Project partners, through the periodic meetings held online and in person, were engaged in the design process of Wiki 5.0, providing suggestions and feedback acting as tester of this strategic tool of the project and contributing to its improvement.

Through in person project meetings and regular online coordination meetings with WP leaders - including the online workshop hosted by Tecnalía on March 19, 2025, and the in person workshops held during the General Meeting in May 2025 – partners actively contributed to both the design and validation process of the Industry 5.0 Assessment Framework, working closely with the 14 use cases involved in the project (who are also project partners).

The engagement of PROSPECTS 5.0 partners in the exploitation process is actively underway. To maximise the added value of the project’s Key Exploitable Results (KERs), partners were invited during the Modena project meeting to reflect on and share their commitment to future actions.

To support this process, a PROSPECTS 5.0 Engagement Map was presented (see below), illustrating the KERs along a timeline and grouping them into four categories (Methods, Evidence, Tools & Guides, Digital Gateways) designed by the exploitation strategy.

This structured approach aims to facilitate stakeholder targeting (of course the list in the figure it is not exhaustive, at this intermediate stage of the project) and better align each partner’s contributions with the project’s strategic exploitation goals and activities (as described in D5.6),

Figure 8 Timeline for partners engagement in the project KERs

6. CONCLUSIONS

The stakeholder engagement activities implemented in the first half of the PROSPECTS 5.0 project has laid a solid foundation for active, inclusive, and meaningful participation across a wide range of actors within and outside the project, allowing to:

- strengthen stakeholder engagement by identifying relevant actors and building meaningful connections across the Industry 5.0 ecosystem, creating the I5.C and connecting with SISTER projects with planned actions;
- nurture the I5.C through a co-creative approach that actively involves project partners, community members, and related initiatives aligned with PROSPECTS 5.0 through the activities planned by the project and the channels used by the communication team;
- highlight the added value of key project outputs – such as Wiki5.0 and the Assessment Framework– by ensuring these tools are shaped by, and useful to, organisations addressing real Industry 5.0 challenges (through validation steps, workshops and feedback collection).

Through a structured process of identification, categorization, and customized engagement, the I5.C has grown into a dynamic network of organisations committed to fostering human-centric, sustainable, and resilient innovation.

Thanks to close collaboration with project partners and the strategic involvement of DIHs, EDIHs, research organisations, enterprises, and policy actors, the project has been able to build synergies and mobilize contributions to key project outcomes, including the Assessment Framework and Wiki5.0.

Moreover, engagement with SISTER projects has proven to be highly valuable, facilitating knowledge exchange, joint planning, and cross-fertilisation activities that enhance the collective impact of Industry 5.0-related initiatives.

Initiatives such as the joint meeting calls, shared communication tools, and recurring coordination meetings have opened the door to future collaboration.

The path forward will build upon this momentum, ensuring that stakeholders remain at the centre of PROSPECTS 5.0. The upcoming activities will further leverage their contributions, ensuring shared ownership of results and real-world relevance of the solutions developed.

Continued interaction, feedback collection, and co-creation will remain the guiding principles in the next phases of the project, strengthening the capacity of the Community of Interest to act as a reference point for Industry 5.0 transformation across Europe. The Figure 9 shows the entire approach:

Figure 9 Pillars of the PROSPECTS 5.0 stakeholder engagement

7. ANNEX 1: Members of the I5.0 Community of Interest

No	Organisation Name	Country	Type	Main interest in the Community of Interest
1	SMILE-DIH	Italy	EDIH	5.0 drivers and benefits
2	CHEDIH	Italy	EDIH	5.0 drivers and benefits
3	EFESTO Sàrl	France	SME	5.0 drivers and benefits
4	Wroclaw University of Science and Technology	Poland	University & HE	5.0 drivers and benefits
5	FIR e.V. at RWTH Aachen University	Germany	R&D organization	5.0 drivers and benefits
6	FUNDECYT-PCTEX	Spain	EDIH	5.0 industry practices for inspiration
7	Transilvania IT Cluster	Romania	Cluster & similar	5.0 industry practices for inspiration
8	Eurecat Technology Centre	Spain	R&D organization	5.0 industry practices for inspiration
9	TRYGONS S.A.	Greece	SME	5.0 industry practices for inspiration
10	Flanders Make	Belgium	R&D organization	5.0 industry practices for inspiration
11	Octave	Belgium	SME	5.0 industry practices for inspiration
12	Klastr MECHATRONIKA	Czech Republic	Cluster & similar	5.0 industry practices for inspiration
13	TRYGONS S.A.	Greece	SME	5.0 industry practices for inspiration
14	B.Braun Avitum Italy spa	Italy	Other	5.0 industry practices for inspiration
15	NextMove	France	Cluster & similar	5.0 industry practices for inspiration
16	BIC Plzen	Czech Republic	Policy stakeholder	5.0 industry practices for inspiration
17	INSIDE Industry Association	Netherlands	Industry Association	5.0 industry practices for inspiration
18	Workplace Innovation Europe	United Kingdom	Other	5.0 industry practices for inspiration
19	Damen Research Development & Innovation Bv	Netherlands	LE	5.0 industry practices for inspiration
20	TNO	Netherlands	R&D organization	5.0 industry practices for inspiration
21	SPRI	Spain	EDIH	5.0 industry practices for inspiration
22	ELMI Ltd.	Latvia	Other	5.0 industry practices for inspiration
23	EIT Manufacturing	France	EU Association	5.0 industry practices for inspiration

24	IRIS EDIH	Spain	EDIH	5.0 scientific knowledge and updates
25	University of Padova	Italy	University & HE	5.0 scientific knowledge and updates
26	B.Braun Avitum Italy spa	Italy	Other	5.0 scientific knowledge and updates
27	HIVA-KU Leuven	Belgium	University & HE	5.0 scientific knowledge and updates
28	CD-EDIH TechCircle	Denmark	EDIH	5.0 scientific knowledge and updates
29	ICOOR	Italy	R&D organization	5.0 scientific knowledge and updates
30	Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of West Bohemia	Czech Republic	University & HE	5.0 scientific knowledge and updates
31	Ericsson	Sweden	Industry Association	5.0 scientific knowledge and updates
32	EDIH ER2Digit	Italy	EDIH	5.0 scientific knowledge and updates
33	DIHNAMO (Digital Innovation Hub Norm	France	EDIH	5.0 use cases
34	TEKNOROT OTOMOTİV ÜRÜNLERİ SAN. VE TİC. A.Ş.	Turkey	LE	5.0 use cases
35	Confindustria Emilia-Romagna Ricerca	Italy	R&D organization	5.0 use cases
36	Zeuko	Spain	SME	5.0 use cases
37	Knowit	Norway	Industry Association	5.0 use cases
38	S-GARD	Germany	SME	5.0 use cases
39	GTW BEARINGS s.r.o.	Czech Republic	Industry Association	5.0 use cases
40	Rgional Develoment Agency of Pilsen Region	Czech Republic	Policy stakeholder	5.0 use cases
41	SMARALD TECH	Romania	SME	5.0 use cases
42	TEKNOROT OTOMOTİV ÜRÜNLERİ SAN. VE TİC. A.Ş.	Turkey	LE	5.0 use cases
43	EIT Manufacturing	France	EU Association	5.0 use cases
44	ARTES 5.0	Italy	EDIH	5.0 use cases
45	CAMELEO	Poland	SME	5.0 use cases

46	Teknorot Otomotiv Ürünleri Sanayi ve Ticaret A.Ş.	Turkey	LE	5.0 use cases
47	Development Centre Novo mesto	Slovenia	EDIH	5.0 use cases
48	AMF Lda.	Portugal	Other	5.0 use cases
49	Siemens	Germany	LE	Other (Advosory board member)
50	PRODUTECH	Portugal	EDIH	Other (All the above)
51	EFFRA	Belgium	Policy stakeholder	Other (All the above)

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